

Supplement 2: *In-vitro* validation

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In-vitro validation of DNA-extraction

Figure 1-S2 *in-vitro* validation of DNA extraction: Comparison of different extraction methods. Comparison of three DNA extraction methods—Blood & Tissue (A), PathoProof (B), and MolYsis (C)—assessing extraction efficiency using two serial dilutions of oxacillin-resistant MRSA (DSM 28766): one diluted in PBS and the other in milk. (+) = PCR-positive control; (-) = PCR-negative control; 1 = 1:10; 2=1:100; 3=1:1000; 4=1:10,000; 5=1:100,000; 6=1:1,000,000; 7=1:10,000,000; 8=1:100,000,000; 9 = extraction negative control; * documented extraction error (no template added)

Figure 2-S2 *in-vitro* validation of MolYsis DNA extraction: Comparison of different sample processing and protocols.

1= Without further processing of the milk sample (small size protocol); 2= Without further processing of the milk sample (medium size protocol); 3= Processed milk sample (skimmed + centrifuged; small size protocol); 4 = Processed milk sample (skimmed; medium size protocol); a= 7.8×10^4 CFU/mL; b= 7.8×10^3 CFU/mL; c= 7.8×10^2 CFU/mL

***In-vitro* validation of *mecA/mecA1* primer**

For the *in vitro* PCR primer validation of primer pair No. 3 (711 bp), two gel images were used to assess sensitivity. The gel image in Figure 3-S2 originates from a selectively enriched MRSA strain (using oxacillin), derived from an initial DNA extract concentration of 1.5×10^5 CFU/mL (determined by McFarland prior to DNA extraction). In this gel image, the LOD could not be determined as it appears to lie outside the tested range ($>1.5 \times 10^5$). However, the PCR-positive control in Figure 1-S2 appears unusually weak, prompting the need for a second gel image for further confirmation. The second gel image (Figure 2-S2) confirms that the LOD for primer pair No. 3 is indeed ($>1.5 \times 10^5$ and establishes it at approximately 4×10^6 genome equivalents. The MRSA sample in Figure 4-S2 was not selectively enriched with oxacillin prior to DNA extraction.

Figure 3-S2 *In-vitro* primer validation: Sensitivity testing of *mecA* primer pair No. 3.

Sensitivity testing of *mecA* primer pair No. 3 (711 bp) using oxacillin-resistant MRSA dilution series (1.50×10^5 to 1.17×10^2). 1 = 1.50×10^5 ; 2 = 1.50×10^4 ; 3 = 7.50×10^3 ; 4 = 3.75×10^3 ; 5 = 1.88×10^3 ; 6 = 9.38×10^2 ; 7 = 4.69×10^2 ; 8 = 2.34×10^2 ; 9 = 1.17×10^2

Figure 4-S2 *In-vitro* primer validation: Sensitivity testing of *mecA* primer pair No. 3.

Sensitivity testing of *mecA* primer pair No. 3 (711 bp) using MRSA dilution series: 1 = MRSA 28766 (14.75 ng/ μ L), 2 = 1:10 dilution, 3 = 1:100 dilution, 4 = 1:1000, 5 = 1:2000, 6 = 1:4000, 7 = 1:8000, 8 = 1: 16000, 9 = 1: 32000, 10 = 1: 64000, 11 = 1:128000, 12 = 1:256000, 13 = 1: 512000, 14 = 1:1024000, 15 = 1:2048000

Figure 5-S2 *In-vitro* primer validation: Sensitivity testing of *mecA1* primer.

Sensitivity testing of *mecA1* primer pair No. 5 (A) & 6 (B) using *M. sciuri* (field isolate No. 12) dilution series. 1 = field isolate No. 12 (118.3 ng/ μ L), 2 = 1:10, 3 = 1:100, 4 = 1:1000, 5 = 1:2000, 6 = 1:4000, 7 = 1: 8000, 8 = 1:16000, 9 = 1:32000, 10 = 1:64000, 11 = 1:128000, 12 = 1:256000; amplicon size = 663bp (A), 466bp (B)

Determining the LOD by means of artificial contamination

Figure 6-S2 Plate counts of dilutions and comparison with expected CFU/mL based on McFarland standard.

Experiment no. 1. The last four dilution steps were plated on blood agar with 100 μ L each. This corresponds to the following concentrations per mL: 1 = 9.375×10^4 , 2 = 9.375×10^3 , 3 = 9.375×10^2 , 4 = 9.375×10^1 . Plate counts of the control strain were significantly lower than expected based on optical density (McFarland standard).

Figure 7-S2 Plate counts of dilutions and comparison with expected CFU/mL based on McFarland standard.

Experiment no. 2. The last four dilution steps were plated on blood agar with 100 μ L each. This corresponds to the following concentrations per mL: 1 = 9.375×10^4 , 2 = 9.375×10^3 , 3 = 9.375×10^2 , 4 = 9.375×10^1 . Plate counts of the control strain were significantly lower than expected based on optical density (McFarland standard).

Figure 8-S2 Determining the LOD by means of artificial contamination.

Experiment No. 1. The LOD of *mecA* was tested with primer No. 4 using a dilution series of MRSA added to pooled bulk milk ($\text{cells} \times \text{mL}^{-1}$ milk), a.b.c. = extraction triplicates, (+) = pure culture extract; 0 = 1.30×10^5 ; 1 = 5.18×10^4 ; 2 = 1.04×10^4 ; 3 = 5.18×10^3 ; 4 = 2.59×10^3 ; 5 = 1.30×10^3 ; 6 = 6.48×10^2 ; 7 = 3.24×10^2 , *mecA* amplicon size = 310bp (Primer No. 4). Due to previous enrichment in the presence of oxacillin, it is assumed that the general cell count corresponds to the *mecA*-positive cell count.

Comparison of MRSA growth on Columbia and Baird-Parker agar

Figure 9-S2 Comparison of the bacterial count of MRSA 28766 on Col- and BP-agar plates
To determine whether the growth of MRSA on Col-agar differs from BP-agar, a dilution series of MRSA 28766 pure culture (starting suspension = 0.5 McFarland, equivalent to 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL) was applied and cultured in parallel on BP (upper row) and Col (lower row). Six serial 1:10 dilutions (D1-D6) were prepared in duplicates, and the final three dilution levels of one duplicate are exemplarily shown in this figure (A, B, C). The CFU-counts of MRSA 28766 were the same on both plates, but smaller colonies were found on BP. (A) D4, > 300 colonies per plate; (B) D5, 109 & 108 colonies per plate; (C) D6, 15 & 11 colonies per plate